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‘निब्बान बोधि’ में प्रकाशित किसी भी लेख अथवा उद्धरण का किसी भी सन्दर्भ में प्रयोग हेतु सम्पादक, प्रकाशक अथवा लेखक की अनुमति की आवश्यकता नहीं है।

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Indriya In Theravāda Buddhism

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The word *Indriya* means Faculty. They are so called because they possess a controlling power in their respective sphere. They are twenty two in number, namely, *Cakkhuindriya*, *Sotindriya*, *Ghāṇindriya*, *Jivhindriya*, *Kāyindriya*, *Manidriya*, *Itthindriya*, *Purisindriya*, *Jīvitindriya*, *Sukhindriya*, *Dukkhindriya*, *Somanassindriya*, *Domanassindriya*, *Upekkhindriya*, *Saddhindriya*, *Viriyindriya*, *Satindriya*, *Samādhindriya*, *Paññindriya*, *Anaññātāññassāmitindriya*, *Aññindriya*, *Aññātāvindriya*. The first six are the sensitive organs. The seventh and eighth are collectively called *bhavindriya*. Vitality (*Jīvitindriya*) is both physical as well as mental. 10th, 11th, 12th, 13th and 14th represent five kinds of feeling. 15th, 16th, 17th, 18th and 19th are treated both as faculties and powers as they influence their co adjuncts and as they overcome their opposing forces. The last three faculties are very important and they pertain to the Supra mundane. A detailed description of the above said twenty two faculties is as follows:

Cakkhu-Indriya

The word *Cakkhu* stands for vision, sense of sight and eye. 'Eye' however, is always in the present article to be understood as the seeing faculty of visual sense, and not as the physical or eye of flesh' (*māmsa cakkhu*). Hence, here *cakkhu* (eye) is not implied in the conventional sense of fleshy eye or eye ball which we perceive. Rather it is used in a technical and specific sense, i.e. 'The quality of perceiving object'. Defining this the **Sammohavinodinī** states - *cakkhatīti cakkhu, rūpaṃ assādeti vibhāveti cā ti attho*.

It means the eye is that which sees, enjoys and clarifies the visible object. Again the meaning of enjoying object in association with consciousness is also implied by this term. Thus *cakkhu* is that which has the ability of perceiving the visible object. To make it further clear, the example of a blind man may be given here. As we know that a blind man has fleshy-eye but he cannot see the things which are found around him because he lacks a specific quality and that specific quality is the ability to see.

Hence, in this background, it may be said that *cakkhu* signifies here not only the fleshy-eye but also the ability to see. It has the characteristic of sentience for phenomena worthy of directly impinging on the object or sentience sprung from action caused by a desire to see. It has the function of drawing consciousness towards the objects. It has the localizing of visual cognition as its manifestation. It is being produced by action caused by desire to see as proximate cause.²

Sota-Indriya

Conventionally *Sota* means the visible form of an ear but in Abhidhammic sense, It refers to specific meaning, 'the ability to hear'. In other words, the state which hears or grasps the sound in association of the consciousness is Sota.³ Explaining this the commentary states that 'it has the characteristic of sentience for phenomena worthy of directly impinging on sounds or of sentient sprung from action caused by a desire to hear sounds. It has the function of drawing consciousness towards sounds. It has the localizing of auditory cognition as its manifestation and it is being produced by action caused by a desire to hear as proximate cause.'⁴

Ghāṇa-Indriya

Generally *Ghāṇa* means nose which is visible. But, technically, it refers to the particular sensitive quality. And this quality is the ability of smelling. Hence, it is defined as *Ghāyati ti ghāṇam*.⁵

Explaining this *Visuddhimagga* states that its characteristic is sensitivity of basic element that is ready from the impact of odorous or produced by action from desire to smell. Its function is to pick up an object among the odorous. It is manifested as the basis or footing of nose consciousness. It is being produced by action and caused by a desire to smell.⁶

Jivhā-Indriya

In general sense, *Jivhā* refers to the fleshy tongue through which one tastes different kinds of food. But in the *Abhidhamma*, it is not applied in this sense. Here, it refers to a specific sensitive quality. And this specific quality is nothing but the ability to taste the sap of food. Hence, it is defined as *āvahāyati ti jivhā*.⁷

Further, explaining this it is said that it has the characteristic of sentience for phenomena worthy of directly impinging on taste or flavour or of sentient sprung from action caused by a desire to taste the flavour. It has the function of drawing consciousness towards flavours. It has the localizing of tongue-consciousness as

its manifestation .It is being produced by action and caused by a desire to taste as proximate cause.⁸

Kāya-Indriya

Conventionally, *Kāya* refers to the visible and gross physical aspect of the human personality. However, in the ultimate sense it bears a technical meaning and in that sense it refers to the sensitive quality of touch. It is this which experiences the different types of physical feeling. Explaining this, the *Visuddhimagga* states that ‘it has the characteristic of sentience for phenomena worthy of directly impinging on the object or sentience sprung from action caused by desire to touch. It has the function of drawing consciousness towards the objects. It has the localizing of body-consciousness as its manifestation. It is being produced by action and caused by a desire to touch.’⁹

Mana-Indriya

Mind or consciousness plays the most important role in the complex machinery of a man. It is mind that either defiles or purifies one. All our words and deeds are coloured by mind or consciousness we experience at such particular moments. “When the mind is unguarded, bodily action is unguarded; speech also is unguarded; thought also is unguarded. When the mind is guarded, bodily action is guarded; speech also is guarded; and thought also is guarded.”¹⁰

“If one speaks or acts with a wicked mind, pain follows one as the wheel, the hoof of the draught-ox”¹¹

“If one speaks or acts with a pure mind, happiness follows one as the shadow that never departs.”¹²

The faculty of mind (*manindriya*) which cognizes ideational object , is not something tangible and perceptible like the other five faculties as they cognize the external world. The eye cognizes the world of colours (*vaṇṇa*) or visible objects, the ear audible sounds, and so forth. The mind, however, cognizes the world of ideas and thoughts. Indriya (faculty), literally, means ‘chief’ or ‘lord’. Forms can only been seen by the faculty of the eye and not by the ear, hearing by the faculty of ear, and so on. When it comes to the world of thoughts and ideas, the faculty of the mind is lord over the mental realm. The eye cannot think thoughts, and collect ideas but it is instrumental in seeing visible forms, the world of colours. It is very important here to understand the function of consciousness. Although there is this functional relationship between the faculties and their objects, for instance, eye with forms, ear with sounds and so on, awareness comes through consciousness.

In other words, sense objects cannot be experienced with the particular sensitivity without the appropriate kind of consciousness. Now when the eye and the form are both present, visual consciousness arises depending on them. Similarly, with ear and sound, and so on; down to mind and mental or ideational objects.

Thus consciousness originates through a stimulus arising at the five sense doors and the mind door, the sixth. As consciousness arises through the interaction of the sense faculties and the sense objects, it is also conditioned and not independent.

Thoughts and ideas are also dependent and conditioned. They depend on the external world which the other five sense - faculties experience. The five faculties come in direct contact with their respective faculties. The mind faculty, however, can experience the sense object, whether it is form, sound, smell, taste or touch already cognized by the sense organs.

Itthindriya & Purisindriya

By faculties of sex we mean *Itthindriya* (faculty of femininity) and *Purisindriya* (faculty of masculinity). In general sense the genital organ or sex marks which are the only distinguished bodily marks in the personality of a female may be understood by this term. The **Dhammasaṅgani** states that the term '*Itthindriya*' means the physical appearance marks, traits and deportment peculiar to a female or the state or condition of femininity.¹³ However, the physical appearance and other features which are peculiar to a female not be expressed by *Itthindriya*. Explaining it, further, the **Aṭṭhasālinī** states that 'the shape of a woman's hand, feet, neck, breast etc. are not like that of man's. The female's lower body is broad, the upper body is less, the hands and feet are small, the mouth is small. The female breast is prominent. The face is without beard or moustache. The dressing of the hair, the weaving of clothes are also unlike those of a man's.'¹⁴

It also states the differences as to habits and deportment. In youth women play with tiny shallow baskets, pestles and mortars, variegated dolls, and weave string with clay-fibre. There is a want of assertion in women's walking, standing, lying down, sitting, eating, and swallowing. Indeed when a man of that description is seen, folk say; he walks, stands etc. like a woman.¹⁵

Hence, it may be said that *Itthittam* has the characteristic of feminine nature. It functions to show that 'this is female'. It manifests as the reason for marks, sign, work and ways of the female.¹⁶

Similarly, the term *purisindriya*, in a general sense, refers only to the sex-marks which distinguish the physical mark of a male. According to *the Dhammasaṅgaṇi*, *Purisindriya* means the physical appearance, marks, traits and deportment peculiar to a male or the state or condition of masculinity.¹⁷ But only the physical appearance and other features which are peculiar only to a male should not be understood by this term. In fact, it is the name of a material quality due to which the physical appearance etc. of a male are different from those of a female. In order to present this difference the *Aṭṭhasālini* states that ‘the hands, feet, neck, breast etc. of a man are unlike those of a woman. For a man’s upper body is broad, the lower body is less broad, his hands and feet are large, the face is large, the breast-flesh is less full; has beard and moustache. There are also differences as to habits and deportment. In youth men play with chariots and ploughs etc., make sand-banks and dig ponds. There is assertion in their walking etc. When a woman is seen taking long strides, etc, folk say, ‘She walks like a man’¹⁸

Hence, in this background, it may be said that it has the characteristic mark of masculine nature. It functions to show that ‘this is male’ and it manifests as the reason for mark, sign, work and ways of the male.¹⁹

Thus, it is seen that *itthindriya* and *purisindriya* are such qualities which determine the differences between male and female as regards their physical form, tone of voice, dispositions, etc. Thus due to these qualities body grows in a particular way such as growth of muscle, appearance of moustache etc.

Jīvitindriya

Here, there are two words-*Jīvita* (life) and *Indriya* (controlling faculty). It is called *Jīvita* because it sustains its co-associates. It is called *Indriya* because it controls its co-associates. *jīvita* is qualified by *Indriya* because it has a dominating influence over other co adjuncts in vivifying them. Although *cetanā* determines the activities of all mental states, it is *Jīvitindriya* that infuses life into *cetanā* and other concomitants. Defining this, the *Dhammasaṅgaṇi* states:

“*Yo tesam rupinam dhammanam āyu thiti yāpanā iriyāna-vattana-patana-Jīvitam Jīvitindriyam, idam tam rūpam Jīvitindriyam.*”²⁰

Jīvitindriya is twofold, namely, psychic life (*Nāma-Jīvitindriya* or *Arūpa Jīvitindriya*) and physical life (*Rūpa-Jīvitindriya*). Mental states are vitalized by psychic life, while material phenomena are vitalized by physical life. As a lotus is sustained by water, an infant is sustained by a nurse, so are mental states and

material phenomena are sustained by *Jīvitindriya*. *Arūpa-Jīvitindriya* is one of the fifty two *cetasikas* (mental states). It is the factor which stabilizes and sustains every type of consciousness as well as those physic factors which arise and perish with it. The *Rūpa-Jīvitindriya* is one of the twenty eight *rūpas*. It is the life of matter, stabilizes and sustains the matter that comes into existence as a result of *kamma*.

One *Rūpa-Jīvitindriya* lasts for seventeen thought moments. Seventeen *Arūpa-Jīvitindriya* arise and perish during the brief life of one *Rūpa-Jīvitindriya*. Both *Arūpa-Jīvitindriya* and *Rūpa-Jīvitindriya* arise at the moment of conception. They simultaneously perish at the moment of decease. Hence, death is regarded as the perishing of this *Jīvitindriya*. Immediately after, due to the power of *kamma*, another *Arūpa-Jīvitindriya* arises in the subsequent birth at the moment of conception. Simultaneous with the arising of one *Arūpa-Jīvitindriya*, there arise three *Rūpa-Jīvitindriyas* in the case of a human being. So far as characteristic etc. are concerned it has the characteristic of life-faculty which maintains co-existent material objects. It may also be understood as the life-principle of the material quality- ‘*Rūpadhammānam āyu Jīvitindriyam*.’ Its function is to make them occur and it manifests in the establishing of their presence. Its proximate cause is the primary elements that are to be sustained.²¹

Sukhindriya

The Word *sukha* is composed of ‘*su*’ easy, and ‘*kha*’ to bear, or to endure. What is easily endured is ‘*sukha*’ i.e. happiness. So, *sukha* (happiness) is a pleasant feeling of the consciousness. It arises due to the attainment of desired object. It causes one in which it arises to feel happy. It develops the associated states. It is also explained at the states which dig out physical and mental obstacles.²²

Ordinary happiness is the gratification of a desire. No sooner is the desired thing gained than we desire some other kind of happiness. So insatiate are our selfish desires. The enjoyment of sensual pleasures is the highest and only happiness to an average person. There is, no doubt, a momentary happiness in the anticipation, gratification and recollection of such material pleasures highly priced by the sensualist, but they are illusory and temporary. Real happiness is found within, and is not to be defined in terms of wealth, power, honour or conquests. The *Aṭṭhasālinī* explains different forms of *sukha*, as follows:

‘Pleasurable feeling’ (*Sukhā vedanā*), ‘root of happiness’ (*sukha-mūla*), ‘pleasurable object’ (*sukhārammaṇa*), ‘cause of happiness’ (*sukhahetu*),

'conditioning state of pleasure' (*sukha-paccayaṭṭhāna*), 'free from troubles' (*abyāpajjha*), 'Nibbāna' (supreme bliss), etc.

Dukkhindriya

The word **Dukkha** has two component parts - 'du' and 'kha'. 'Du' means with difficulty (*dukkarena*), 'kha' means bearing (*khamanam*); that which is born or taken disagreeably is *dukkha*. So the term *dukkha* means 'painful feeling', 'basis of pain', 'object of pain', 'cause of pain', 'conditioning state of pain', etc.

In the **Dhammacakkappavattanasutta** the Buddha enumerates eight divisions of *dukkha*, namely, (1) birth is suffering, (2) decay is suffering, (3) disease is suffering, (4) death is suffering, (5) association with the unloved is suffering, (6) separation from the loved is suffering, (7) not to get what one wants is suffering, (8) in brief, the five aggregates as an object of clinging is suffering.

When the Buddha addresses *devas* and men he speaks of eight kinds of *dukkha*. When he addresses only men he speaks of twelve. Instead of *byādhi* (disease), he says *soka* (grief), *parideva* (lamentation), *dukkha* (pain), *domanassa* (displeasure), *upāyāsa* (despair). All these five are included in *byādhi*, which embraces both physical and mental disharmony. *Soka*, *domanassa* and *upāyāsa* are mental, while *dukkha* and *parideva* are physical.

Even the Buddha, a perfect being who has destroyed all defilements, had to endure physical suffering caused by diseases and accidents. His last illness caused him much physical suffering. As a result of *Devadatta's* hurling a rock to kill him, his foot wounded by a splinter which necessitated an operation. Sometimes he was compelled to starve. Due to the disobedience of his own pupils, he was compelled to retire to a forest for three months.

Somanassindriya

Somanassa is an abstract noun formed of 'su', good and 'mana', mind. Literally, the term *somanassa* means good-mindedness i.e. a pleasurable feeling. The **Vibhaṅga** says:

"Therein, what is joy (*somanassa*)?"

Mental pleasure, mental happiness, felt pleasure and happiness born of mind - contact, pleasurable and happy feeling born of mind-contact - this is called joy'.²³

Domanassindriya

The word *Domanassa* has two component parts - 'Du' and 'mana'. Here, 'Du' stands for bad and 'mana' signifies mind. Therefore *Domanassa* means bad mindedness i.e. a displeasurable feeling. According to the **Vibhaṅga** :

“ Therein, what is grief (*domanassa*) ?

Mental displeasure, mental pain, the felt displeasure and pain born of mind-contact, the unpleasurable and painful born of mind-contact - this called grief. ”²⁴

Upekkhā-Indriya

Upekkhā consists of two words - 'upa' and 'ikkha'.

Here, *upa* means impartially, justly (*yuttito*), and *ikkha*, to see, to view, to look. Thus, *upekkhā* is the name of viewing impartially i.e. neither with attachment nor with aversion. It is the indifferent state of mind. Attachment and aversion are eliminated by *upekkhā*. Impartial attitude is its characteristic. Here, *upekkhā* does not mean mere natural feeling, but a sterling virtue is implied thereby. Equanimity is its equivalent. *Upekkhā* embraces all good and bad ones, loved and unloved ones, agreeable and disagreeable things, pleasure and pain and all such similar opposite pairs. Thus it is viewing an object with a balanced mind. The **Aṭṭhasālinī** states - “This is impartially (*majjhataṃ*) in connection with the object and implies a discriminative knowledge (*paricchindanakam nāṇam*)”.

Saddhā-Indriya

The word *Saddhā* has also two components - *sam* and *dah*. Here *sam* means well, and *dah*, to establish, to place, to put. Thus *saddhā* is well-established confidence in the Buddha, *Dhamma* and Saṅgha.²⁵

But this *saddhā* is not a blind faith. In fact, it is confidence based on knowledge which helps in the purification of mind. Hence, it is compared to the water-purifying gem of the universal monarch. This particular gem, when thrown into water, causes mud and water-weeds to subside. The water is consequently purified. In the same way *saddhā* purifies the mind of its defilements. The **Dhammasaṅgaṇī** explains *saddhā* as follows:

‘The faith which on that occasion is trusting in, the professing confidence in, the sense of assurance, faith; faith as a faculty and as a power.’²⁶

Saddhā is the intuitive knowledge gathered in past births. It has the characteristic of having faith or trusting. Its function is purify the associated

states, like a water purifying gem and its function is to enter into the associated states as a faith, like the crossing of the floods. Freedom from pollution or decision is its manifestation and an object of the worthy-faith is its proximate cause.²⁷

Viriya-Indriya

Vira of *virīya* is one who strenuously carries his work uninterruptedly. *Viriya* is defined as the state or action of energetic persons.²⁸

Or, it is that which is carried out methodically.²⁹

Viriya has the characteristic of supporting³⁰ (*upatthambana*), upholding (*paggaḥaṇa*), sustaining (*ussahana*). As an old house is supported by new pillars, even so concomitants are aided and supported by *virīya*. Just as a strong reinforcement would help an army to hold on instead of retreating even so *virīya* upholds or uplifts its concomitants.

Viriya is regarded as a controlling factor (*Indriya*) because it overcomes idleness. It is also regarded as one of the five powers (*Bala*) because it cannot be shaken by its opposite idleness. *Viriya* serves as one of the four means of accomplishing one's ends (*iddhipāda*). It is this *virīya* that appears as four modes of supreme efforts (*sammappadhāna*). *Viriya* is sublimated as one of the seven factors of enlightenment (*bojjhaṅga*). Finally it has been elevated to one of the eight members of the noble path (*aṭṭhaṅgika -magga*) as *sammā vāyāma* (right effort).

The **Aṭṭhasālinī** states that *virīya* should be regarded as the root of all achievements. Effort, exertion, energy are its equivalents. Keeping these things in mind, it is said that supporting or upholding the co-existent states are its characteristic.³¹ Its function is to strengthen the co-existent states. It is manifested as opposition to give way to the sloth and torpor. Basic condition of making energy is its proximate cause.³²

Sati-Indriya

The word *Sati* is derived from *Sar*, to remember. The literal meaning of the term *sati* is awareness or mindfulness.³³ But in a specific sense, it is used here to signify the mental state which makes the associated *dhammas* alert at the time when something appears before the mind. In fact, it is the state which keeps the sense-organs under control and does not allow them to get involved with their respective objects. Here, the act of seeing is for the sake of seeing only, the act of

hearing is for the sake of hearing only and so on. Mindfulness prevents undesirable objects from entering into the mind; it allows only those factors which are desirable and helpful for the benefit of the mind. *Sati-indriya* is able to check all the currents of craving (e.g. lust for sensual pleasure, lust for repeated existence, and lust for destruction of others) flowing in the world.

In other words, *sati* serves to keep the true nature of the object before the mind, firmly and properly. Because of this strong fixation in the object, it is compared to a gate-keeper (*dovārika*) standing at the senses to allow entering only moral thoughts into the mind. It is essential to develop *sati* for peace and happiness.

In the *Satipaṭṭhāna sutta* various methods to develop *sati* are described in detail. It is said that when it is highly developed, one acquires the power of remembering past births. This *sati* is regarded as one of the factors of the Noble Eightfold Path. In fact, it tends to present before oneself good things without allowing them to be forgotten. The **Dhammasaṅgaṇi** explains *sati* as follows:

“The mindfulness which on that occasion is recollecting, calling back to mind; the mindfulness which is remembering, bearing in mind, the opposite of superficiality and of obliviousness; mindfulness as faculty, mindfulness as power, right mindfulness.”³⁴

According to commentary, ‘it has the characteristic of not wobbling. Its function is not to forget. It is manifested as guarding, or as the state of confronting an objective field. Its proximate cause is strong perception, or the foundations of mindfulness concerned with the body, and so on.’³⁵

Samādhi- Indriya

‘*Samādhi*’ is one-pointedness of the mind. It is concentration of the mind on one object. It teaches us to get control over our mind for not getting involved in various objects of lure.

Concentration has been studied and analysed in different ways and contexts, by which it has become manifold and many sided. But in brief, it has been defined as the collectedness or one-pointedness of moral thought.³⁶ Due to concentration, consciousness and psychic factors are placed and fixed on a particular object without wavering or scattering. So, it can be said that concentration has been applied in the sense of placing (*samādhāna*) or setting well of consciousness and psychic factors fittingly well in single object.³⁷

So far as the characteristic, essence, manifestation and proximate cause of concentration are concerned, it has been said that non-wavering, not being confused, distracted or disturbed are the marks or characteristic of concentration.

³⁸ It points out that the five constituents of meditation (*jhānaṅgas*), viz, applied thinking (*vitakka*), sustained thinking (*vicāra*), rapture (*pīti*), ease (*sukha*), and concentration (*ekaggatā*), always help in the gradual concentration only and keep mind safe from distraction and wavering. Since, concentration destroys wavering of mind; destruction of wavering can be marked as the essence or function of concentration. Again, its manifestation or expression is not shaking or not deviating from the desired objective (*avikampanapaccupaṭṭhāno*) ³⁹. We have seen that once mind starts its efforts for concentration with the help of five factors of meditation, there is no more distraction from the object, rather mind fixes itself on that object, gradually one – pointedness gets intensified and ultimately it gets full concentration. In this way, concentration manifests or expresses itself through not shaking or not deviating from the desired object. Happiness or ease (*sukha*) has been said to be the proximate or immediate cause (*padaṭṭhāna*) of concentration. ⁴⁰

After practising meditation thoroughly, mind becomes pure, tranquil, subtle and pliable. And then with such a mind, the *yogāvacara* enters into the domain of *paññā* (wisdom) and developing *paññā* sincerely, in due course, he understands the true nature of *dhammas*, that there is nothing as such that can be treated as permanent, that everything is subject to suffering, and that there is nothing as an unchangeable soul or essence. In this way, concentration prepares mind for developing wisdom.

Paññindriya

The word *paññā* has two terms-‘*pa*’ and ‘*ñā*’. Here, *Pa* means rightly and *ñā* means to know. Literally, *paññā* means right knowing, right understanding, right comprehending etc. But in Abhidhammic sense, it is the mental state which comprehends or perceives the true nature of the conditioned things. In fact, it is the knowledge or clear understanding of all the conditioned things as possessing the three salient features of impermanence, suffering and egolessness. ⁴¹ The **Visuddhimagga** defines it as ‘*kusalacittasampayuttam vipassanāñāṇam paññā*’. ⁴² It means the insight knowledge associated with moral consciousness is *paññā*. As *paññā* dominates in understanding the real nature and as it overcomes ignorance, it is called a controlling faculty (*Indriya*) ⁴³. Since *paññā* is the complete understanding of subject it has got highest rank among various types of knowledge and comprehension. What are the other types of the knowledge? They

are *saññā* (perception) and *viññāṇa* (consciousness). The former perceives the impression of an object such as blue, green, etc. but does not realize its characteristic feature.⁴⁴ Similarly, the '*viññāṇa*' perceives the impression and also realizes its characteristic but does alienate itself from clinging to object.⁴⁵ Hence, in this background, the *paññā* not only penetrates into the intrinsic nature of an object but also tries to detach from the object.

In the **Milindapañha**, *paññā* has been defined as having the characteristic mark of 'cutting off' (*chedanalakkhaṇā paññā*)⁴⁶ and also as possessing enlightenment as mark - *obhāsanalakkhaṇā paññā*.⁴⁷ It is so as it dispels the darkness of ignorance, causes the radiance of knowledge to arise, makes the light of intelligence to shine forth, and makes the *Noble Truth* clear. In its light one perceives the impermanency of all beings and things, the suffering that is inherent in individuality and the absence of any soul.

It has the characteristic of penetrating into the true nature of phenomena. It has the function of dispelling the darkness of bewilderment or ignorance. The manifestation of wisdom is not being bewildered.⁴⁸ He, who is concentrated, knows and sees a thing as it really is and, thus, concentration is the proximate cause of wisdom.

Anaññātāññassāmīndriya, Aññindriya, Aññātāvindriya

In the **Dhammasaṅgaṇi**'s enumeration of states, the factor of wisdom enters into the supramundane *jhānas* as three new faculties spread out over the four paths and fruits (*magga and phala*). These three are the faculty of 'I shall know the unknown' (*anaññātāññassāmīndriya*), the faculty of final knowledge (*aññindriya*), and the faculty of the completion of final knowledge (*aññātāvindriya*).⁴⁹ The first is present in the first path, the second in the six intermediate states from the first fruition through the fourth path, and the third in the fourth fruition, the fruit of arahataship. The faculty of "I shall know the unknown" is the wisdom - faculty of one standing on the path of stream - entry, the "unknown" being, according to the commentary, the deathless state of *nibbāna* or the four Noble Truths, neither of which has been known before in beginningless *samsāra*.⁵⁰

The faculty of final knowledge is the faculty of wisdom in those at the intermediate stages of progress, while the faculty of the completion of final knowledge is the fully matured wisdom of the arahataship. None of these faculties is present as such in mundane *jhāna*.

Notes & References:

1. Sammohavinodinī (S.V.) 2.1 , p.46 ; Visuddhimagga (Vism.) , p. 1080
2. Tattha rūpābhīghātārahabhūtappasādalakkhaṇaṃ , daṭṭhukāmatānidānakamma- samuṭṭhāna bhūtappasādalakkhaṇaṃ vā cakkhu, rūpesu aviñcharasaṃ cakkhu- viññāṇassa ādhārabhāvapaccupaṭṭhānaṃ , daṭṭhakāmatānidānakammajabhūta- padaṭṭhānaṃ . - Vism. 14.32, p.967; Aṭṭhasālinī (Asl.) 4.38 , p. 25
3. Sunati etena, viññāpādhiṭṭhitam sayam vā sunatī ti sotam . - Vism. 14.32, p.966
4. Saddābhīghātārahabhūtappasādalakkhaṇaṃ, sotukāmatānidānakamma- samuṭṭhānabhūtappasādalakkhaṇaṃ vā sotam , saddesu aviñcharasaṃ , sotaviññāṇassa ādhārabhāvapaccupaṭṭhānaṃ, sotukāmatānidānakammaja- bhūtapadaṭṭhānaṃ . - Vism.14.32 , p. 968
5. S.V. 2.1 , p.46
6. Gandhābhīghātārahabhūtappasādalakkhaṇaṃ ghāyitukāmatānidānakamma- samuṭṭhānabhūtappasādalakkhaṇaṃ vā ghāṇaṃ, gandhesu aviñcharasaṃ, ghāṇaviññāṇassa ādhārabhāvapaccupaṭṭhānaṃ ghāyitukāmatānidānakamma- jabhūtapadaṭṭhānaṃ . - Vism. 14.32, p.968
7. S.V. 2.1, p.46
8. Rasabhīghātārahabhūtappasādalakkhaṇo sayitukāmatānidānakammamuṭṭhāna- bhūtappasādalakkhaṇā vā jivhā, rasesu aviñjanarasa, jivhāviññāṇassa ādhārabhāva- paccupaṭṭhāna, sayitukāmatānidana kammajabhūtapadaṭṭhāna . - Asl. 4.38, p. 252
9. Phoṭṭhabbābhīghātārahabhūtappasādalakkhaṇo, phusitukāmatānidānakamma- samuṭṭhānabhūtappasādalakkhaṇo vā kāyo, phoṭṭhabbesu aviñcharaso , kāyaviññāṇassa ādhārabhāvapaccupaṭṭhāna, phusitukāmatānidānakammajabhūta- padaṭṭhāno . - Vism. 14.32, p.969
10. Asl. 4.38 , p.68 ; the expositor 1, p.91
11. Dhammapada , p.1
12. Ibid.
13. Yam itthiyā itthilingam itthinimittam itthikuttam itthakappo itthattam itthibhāvo idam tam vuccati itthindriyam . - Dhammasaṅgaṇi (Dhms.) 2.97.10 , p.173
14. Asl. 4.61, p . 258
15. Ibid.
16. Itthibhāvalakkhaṇam itthindriyam, Itthīti pakāsanarasaṃ, itthilinganimitta- kuttakappānam kāraṇabhāvapaccupaṭṭhānam . -Vism.14.37 , p.976
17. Yam purisassa purisalingam purisanimittam purisakuttam, purisakappo purisattam purisabhāvo - idam tam vuccati purisindriyam - Dhms., 97.11 , p.173
18. Asl. 4.63 , p.259
19. Purisabhāvalakkhaṇam , purisindriyam puriso ti pakāsanarasaṃ , purisalinga- nimittakuttakappānam kāraṇabhāvapaccupaṭṭhānam .' -Vism. 14.37, p. 979
20. It means the persistence of these corporeal states, their subsistence, their going on , their being kept going on, their progress, continuance, preservation of life as faculty, this is what is Jīvitindriya .
21. Sahajarūpānupālanālakkaṇam Jīvitindriyam tesam pavattanarasaṃ , tesam yeva ṭhapanā paccupaṭṭhānaṃ , yāpayitabbabhūtapadaṭṭhānaṃ . -Vism. 14.38 , p.977
22. Suṭṭhu vā khādati khaṇati cā kāyacittabādhamaṃ ti sukham . -Vism; 4.83, p.308

23. Vibhaṅga (Vibh.), p.271
24. Ibid.
25. Saddahatīti saddhā . - Abhidhammatthavibhāvinītikā (Vibht.) 2.5, p.45
26. Buddhist psychology, p.14
27. Sā Saddahanalakkhaṇā okappanalakkhaṇā vā , pāsādanarasā udakappasāda- kamaṇi viya, pakkhandanaraso vā, oghuttarano viya, akālussiyapaccupaṭṭhāno, adhimutti paccupaṭṭhānaṃ vā , saddheyavatthupadaṭṭhānā. -Vism. 14.97, p.1037
28. Virānaṃ bhāvo kammaṃ .
29. Vidhinā vā nayena upāyena irayitabbaṃ pavattetabbaṃ ti viriyaṃ . -Asl. 3.217, p. 99
30. Upatthambanalakkhaṇaṃ viriyaṃ - Milindpañho (Miln.) , p.28
31. Taṃ panetaṃ upatthambanalakkhaṇaṃ ca viriyaṃ pagghanalakkhaṇaṃ ca. - Asl. 3.218, p.99
32. Sahajātadhammānaṃ upatthambhanarasāṃ, asansidanabhāvapaccupaṭṭhānaṃ viriyārambhavatthupadaṭṭhānaṃ vā . - Ibid. 3.219, p.99
33. Saranti tāya sayāṃ vā sarati saraṇamattameva vā esā ti sati.-Vism, 14.98.p.1037 Saraṇā sati. -Vibht. 2.5, p.46
34. Buddhist Psychology, p. 16
35. Sā apilāpanalakkhaṇā asammosarasā, āraḍḍhapaccupaṭṭhānā, visayābhimukkha- bhāvapaccupaṭṭhānā vā , thirasaññāpadaṭṭhānā , okāyadisatipaṭṭhānā padaṭṭhānā vā. - Vism. 14.98, p.1037
36. Kusalacittakaggatā samādhi. - Ibid. , p. 83
37. Samādhānaṭṭhena samādhi. - Ibid.
38. Avikkhepalakkhaṇo samādhi. - Ibid. , p. 189
39. Ibid.
40. Ibid.
41. Pakārena jānāti aniccādivasena avabujjhatīti paññā .-Vibht. 2.7, p.48
42. Vism. 14.2, p.946
43. Sā eva yathāsabhāvāvabodhene adhipaccayogato indriyaṃ ti paññindriyaṃ . -Vibht. 2.7, p.48
44. Saññā tāva nīlādivasena sañjānanamattaṃ karoti, lakkhaṇappaṭivedhaṃ kātū na sakkoti. - Vibht.2.7, p.48
45. Viññānaṃ lakkhaṇappaṭivedhaṃ pi sādheti, ussukketvā pana maggaṃ papetuṃ na sakkoti.
46. Miln. 2.1.14, p.30
47. Ibid.
48. Ettha pana dhammasabhāvappaṭivedhalakkhaṇā paññā , dhammānaṃ sabhāva- paṭicchādanamohandhakāraviddhamsanarasāṃ , asammohapaccupaṭṭhānaṃ. Samāhito yāthābhūtam jānāti passatī ti vacanato pana samādhi tassā padaṭṭhānaṃ . -Vism. 14.7, p.950
49. Dhms. , p.77,99,138
50. Asl. , p.261